

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTENSIVE READING APPROACH

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The Effectiveness of Intensive Reading Approach

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Abstract

This study aimed to find out the effects of intensive reading approach on pupil's reading comprehension in Tubigan Elementary School in Initao, Division of Misamis Oriental. Specifically, the study sought to describe the profile of the respondents in the study; to determine the performance of the Grade IV pupils in the pretest and posttest conducted to experimental and control group; discuss how the reading comprehension is enhanced through the intensive reading approach; disclose the significance difference between the performance of the Grade IV pupils exposed to intensive reading approach and to those who are in the traditional group; and discuss to what extent does intensive reading approach contribute to Grade IV pupils reading comprehension. This study applied the quasi-experimental research design. Pretest was administrated before the conduct of the study while posttest was given at the end of the study. The difference of the test scores was compared using t-test. The study revealed a significant difference on the performance of the respondents when intensive reading approach was applied considering the difference of the pre-test and post-test results. This indicates that the application of intensive reading had a positive influence on the learners reading comprehension because their reading comprehension has actually improved significantly.

Keywords: *intensive reading approach, reading comprehension*

Introduction

In learning the English language, students should be aware of its four learning skills. These learning skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Among the learning skills which have to be mastered by the students is the reading skill. Reading is not only a source of information and a pleasurable activity but also as a means of consolidating and extending one's knowledge of the language. In reading skill, the students are expected to draw meaning from printed page and interpret this information appropriately. This means comprehending and interpreting the information of the text are important. It implies that students need to learn a considerable amount of information from a text.

However, comprehension may mean a variety of things. It may indicate being able to recall the text, to answer questions about character motives, to extract themes, to critique the structure, or a combination of these activities. Although each kind of comprehension leads readers to adopt somewhat different goals and processes, together they share an important feature. They all require that readers construct a mental "picture" of the text: a representation in memory of the textual information and its interpretation. Such mental representations ideally can be easily accessed, manipulated, and applied to any number of situations. Thus, comprehension is a process of reading (Van den Broek & Kremer, 2010).

The reader's motivation to make sense of the text they read, connecting ideas to their prior knowledge is successful reading comprehension. Readers usually comprehend at the sentence level; however, in a bid to decode the text, a reader may occasionally descend to the word level. Comprehension can occur during the act of reading or after the act itself, as the reader reflects on what they've read (Fountas & Pinnell, 2016). What that suggests is that, at least, the reader should gain some understanding of the message that is being conveyed by the author.

Wren (2011) claims that to truly comprehend text is to make connections between the information in the text and the information in the reader's head, that is, to draw inferences about the author's meaning and to evaluate the quality of the message. The ability to comprehend text passages is essential for achievement in school and learning throughout life. If students do not learn to read and comprehend efficiently, the path is blocked to every subject they encounter in their school years. These students who fall behind in reading skills will never catch up with their schoolmates who become fluent readers.

Although the ability to read and comprehend words and their components is a basic, foundational skill, helping students achieve this skill, without creating disinterest in reading, is the educational challenge. Acquisition of this foundation allows the student to benefit from other activities that promote further advancement: extended practice reading a variety of texts, with close checks on comprehension; reading texts for different purposes; gaining background knowledge relevant to what is being read. Intensive reading has been suggested as a teaching strategy to enhance students' reading comprehension of a text. Considering this educational challenge, an appropriate teaching strategy or approach should be applied to make students become active, enjoy, and comprehend the main point of the reading text.

Intensive reading, as suggested by Nuttall (2012), is for a high degree of comprehension and retention over a long period of time. The aim is to arrive at an understanding, not only of what the text means, but of how the meaning is produced. In addition, Patel and Jain (2011) give emphasis to intensive reading as text reading or passage reading. In this reading, the students read the text or passage to get the specific information. Intensive reading is usually concerned with shorter text.

Thus, to contribute a dynamic way of teaching that encourages students to explore and synthesize texts, helping them to develop comprehension skills that go beyond trying to simply find the correct answer, the researcher is highly motivated to conduct reading comprehension enhancement through intensive reading approach.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the effects of intensive reading approach on pupil's reading comprehension in Tubigan Elementary School in Initao, Division of Misamis Oriental during school year 2017-2018. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. gender;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment of parents;
 - 1.3. family monthly income;
 - 1.4. attitudes towards reading;
 - 1.5. study habits;
 - 1.6. parent's follow-up;
 - 1.7. availability of reading materials, and
 - 1.8. availability of gadgets?
2. What is the performance of the Grade IV pupils in pretest and posttest conducted to the following groups:
 - 2.1. control, and
 - 2.2. experimental?
3. What is the performance of the Grade IV pupils in the posttest conducted to the following groups:
 - 3.1. intensive reading approach, and
 - 3.2. traditional approach?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the Grade IV pupils to intensive reading approach and to those who are in the traditional group in the pre test and posttest conducted?
5. To what extent does intensive reading approach contribute to Grade IV pupils reading comprehension?

Methodology

Research Design

This study applied the quasi-experimental research design. This involved a pretest and posttest conducted to the respondents. Shuttleworth (2011) asserts that quasi-experimental design involves selecting groups, upon which a variable is tested. Since the most common form of a quasi-experimental study includes a pre-post test design, it was necessary to have both an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was taught reading through the intensive reading strategy, while the control group was taught reading through the traditional method. Pretest and posttest were administered before and after the reading activities, respectively. This process was to compare the experimental and control groups regarding the degree of change that happened as a result of the treatment (intensive reading).

Respondents

The Grade IV pupils of Tubigan Elementary School in Initao, Division of Misamis Oriental during the school year 2017-2018 were the respondents of the study. Since there were two sections of Grade IV classes, one section acted as the experimental group (intensive reading approach) and the other section was the control group (traditional approach). Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by section. The total number of respondents was 66 pupils. Both Grade IV sections were being taught by the researcher in English subject.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Grade and Section</i>	<i>Designation</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
IV - Amazing	Intensive Reading Approach (Experimental Group)	33
IV- Admirable	Traditional Approach (Control Group)	33
Total		66

The purposive or deliberate sampling of the non-random sampling strategy was applied in the selection of respondents. As the name implies, this strategy of sampling intentionally used judgment in the selection of respondents. Hence, the two sections of Grade IV pupils of Tubigan Elementary School were selected because of a purpose.

Instruments

This study utilized three types of survey questionnaires, the researcher-made questionnaire (Part 1), the adopted questionnaires (Parts 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) and the pretest and posttest questionnaires. Part I gathered the respondent's gender, highest educational attainment and family monthly income. Parts 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 inquired the respondents' attitudes towards reading, study habit, parent's follow-up,

availability of reading materials and availability of gadgets. The questionnaires for attitudes towards reading and study habit were measured using 4-point Likert scale of agreement. The options ranged from “never” (1) to “always” (4). While questionnaires for parent’s follow-up, availability of reading materials and availability of gadgets were measured by the options “yes or no”. The pretest and posttest questionnaires were based on the target skills for reading comprehension which consists of 40 items.

The respondents performance in reading comprehension was measured by pretest and posttest. The pretest was administered to both the experimental group (intensive reading approach) and the control group (traditional approach) before the actual study. Posttest was performed after all the intensive reading activities were finished.

Procedure

The researcher requested a letter of recommendation from the Dean of the Graduate School, PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College, to conduct a study. After seeking permission and allowed to conduct the study by the Division Superintendent of Misamis Oriental and the District Supervisor, the researcher went to the principal to float the questionnaire.

The pretest was administered to all the respondents before the intensive reading approach treatment. The intensive reading group was taught through the intensive reading teaching approach, while the traditional group was taught in the traditional method. The lessons delivered were the topics during the current grading period. Content of the lessons (stories) were drawn from the textbook presently use in Grade IV level. The intensive reading approach group was taught in the morning session whereas the traditional group in the afternoon session.

Posttest was performed after all the lessons were presented to both groups. The posttest retained all the questions of the pretest but of different sequence. The posttest was administered to measure any changes in the pupil’s reading comprehension level and confidentiality of their answers was assured by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Having collected and recorded the data gathered in this study, the researcher employed the following statistical tools:

Descriptive statistics such as percentage, weighted mean and standard deviation were computed to describe the distribution of test scores of the respondents in both pretest and posttest, attitudes towards reading and study habits, parent’s follow-up, availability of reading materials and availability of gadgets. The t-test was performed to reveal significant difference of scores of the respondents obtained from the pretest and posttest.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of: gender, highest educational attainment of parents, family monthly income, attitudes towards reading, study habits, parent’s follow-up, availability of reading materials, and availability of gadgets?

Table 2. *Distribution of the Respondents’ Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	36	54.55
Female	30	45.45
Total	66	100.00

Table 2 reveals that 36 (54.55%) of the Grade IV pupils are males and 30 (45.45%) are females. This implies that there are more male pupils in the Grade IV class in Tubigan Elementary School. The dominant population of male pupils is likely to happen during the school year 2016-2017. As reported by school heads in the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS) for school year 2015-2016, the total enrolment of Grade III in public elementary schools (as of September 30, 2015) is 2,216,155. Of this Grade III total enrolment, 1,168,709 (52.74%) are males and 1,047,446 (47.26%) are female (Llego, 2015). Even in the total enrolment of elementary pupils (Grade I to Grade IV), which is 14,849,646, there are 7,764,982 (52.00%) male pupils compared to 7,129,664 (48.00%) female pupils.

Long distance between the home and school could have prevented the female pupil’s access to education. Availability of schools within a reasonable distance from home is often a pre-condition for school participation particularly for girls. Many schools, particularly those in barangay areas, are not only far from homes, but most pupils have to walk long distance through difficult terrain in order to attend school. Since male pupils are perceived to have more endurance in walking than female pupils, their participation in school is better. In addition, some parents may have a preference for educating their sons than the daughters, given better labor market opportunities for males (T’shome, 2012).

Given that reading is a learned skill its educational implications remind the crucial role parents play in promoting children’s reading development. In other words, parents could provide young children with relevant early home experiences, in order to diminish possible handicap on reading skills. More specifically, they could encourage the child to tell what he or she thinks or feels, to build a rich vocabulary by reading and talking about new words, to play sound games, to promote phonological awareness helping them to recognize syllables and individual sounds in words, to combine or blend sounds into words, and to manipulate syllables in words.

Additionally, elementary school teachers have to make learning meaningful, taking into account the interests and needs of children, to integrate reading into other activities and to show that reading is an essential, everyday skill with practical value (Davidson & Snow, 1995 cited by Vlachos & Papadimitriou, 2015).

Table 3. *Distribution of Respondents' Parent's Highest Educational Attainment*

Father		Parent's Highest Educational Attainment	Mother	
f	%		f	%
17	25.75	Elementary Level	3	4.55
3	4.55	Elementary Graduate	10	15.15
11	16.67	High School Level	12	18.18
24	36.36	High School Graduate	20	30.30
1	1.51	Vocational Course Graduate	1	1.51
2	3.03	College Level	12	18.18
5	7.58	College Graduate	5	7.58
3	4.55	Graduate Studies	3	4.55
66	100	Total	66	100.00

Table 3 presents that 24 (36.36%) of the respondents had father whose highest educational attainment was high school graduate. In the research locale of the study, most of the male parents are engaged in fishing, agriculture, beach resort workers and construction industry laborers. Although, many of the occupations do not need higher educational attainment, still the possession of a high school diploma is the minimum educational qualification. The proximity of the high school to the barangay could have encouraged most of the respondents' male parents to finish the secondary education level. Being a high school graduate in the area not only helped the male parents increase their confidence and self-esteem but also made them as a role model to their children, relatives, as well as friends, to motivate their children to go school.

The highest educational attainment of the respondent's mothers was high school graduate with a frequency of 20 (30.30%). As expected the respondents' female parents have similarity in terms of highest education attainment with the respondent's male parents. Parental education is an important index of socioeconomic status and a predictor to children's educational and behavioral outcomes. A child exposed to parents who model achievement-oriented behavior (e.g., obtaining advanced degrees; reading frequently; encouraging a strong work ethic) and provide achievement-oriented opportunities (e.g., library and museum trips; after-school enrichment programs; educational books and videos) develop the guiding belief that achievement is to be valued, pursued, and anticipated. This belief then in turn promotes successful outcomes across development, including high school graduation, the pursuit of higher learning, and the acquisition of high-prestige occupations (Dubow, Boxer & Huesmann, 2011).

Only one (1.51%) of the respondents' parents was a vocational course graduate. The likely explanation is that most respondents' parents during their high school education preferred the general education curriculum than the vocational courses. Vocational course may induce early employment advantages due to the combined academics and specialized skills in a more hands-on manner, often providing the platform for a more interactive and engaging learning experience. However, these advantages are likely eroded by technological change (Hanushek, Schwerdt, Woessmann, & Zhang, 2016).

In contrast, the general education high school graduates received standard education to pursue certain career path. Parents who socialize their children towards higher levels of educational achievement and occupational success by modeling achievement-related behaviors foster positive expectations for academic performance. The importance of parental education on child's educational outcome could influence the future of their child (Dubow, Boxer, & Huesmann, 2011).

Performing a comparison between the general education high school graduates and vocational course graduates may provide a better sense in terms of the employment returns. It would not be surprising to find a job quality gap in favor of vocational course graduates especially for young workers. However, the situation is visible only during the early stages of their labor market experience. This comparison may gain substantial policy relevance because the discussions on the value of vocational course graduates and general education high school graduates will be mostly to target the demands of the labor market (Amos, 2016).

Table 4. *Distribution of the Respondents' Family Monthly Income*

Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Php 20,000.01 and above	1	1.51
Php 15,000.01 - Php 20,000.00	4	6.06
Php 10,000.01 - Php 15,000.00	5	7.58
Php 5,000.01 - Php 10,000.00	22	33.33
Php 5,000.00 and below	34	51.52
Total	66	100.00

Table 4 illustrates that 34 (51.52%) of the respondents have family monthly income of Php 5,000.00 and below. As explained earlier,

in Barangay Tubigan most of the people are engaged in fishing, agriculture, maintenance workers or laborers in beach resorts and house constructions. These kinds of employment involved many laborers and some unskilled workers that earn very low wages. Basing on the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) of Philippine Statistics Authority (2015), the respondent's family belonged to Class E family which is the lowest level of social class in the Philippines. Class E which comprised 30% of the population received an annual income of Php 62,000.00.

The respondent who claimed to have a family monthly income of Php 20,000.00 and above with a frequency of 1 (1.51%) could have belonged to the few business entrepreneur of Barangay Tubigan. Since the FIES declared that the average family Income in its latest survey results of 2015 is estimated at Php 22,000 monthly, it follows that the respondent's family belonged to Class D. This class category represents the largest bulk of families in the Philippines: 60%. Therefore, six (6) out of every 10 Filipinos belong to Class D. Judging by this huge percentage, it can be said the "masa" population in the country is Class D.

The family income, high or low, can have its impact on student's achievement in all their learning years. The lower the income of the families, the lower will be the probability of sending their children to school. Parents who have low income generally do not read to their children, have difficulties to understand or learn as fast as others (McMahon, 2012). In addition, if parents do not have the necessary skills of providing varied and extensive vocabulary, then their children will be lagging behind other students of the same age (Farzanite, 2013).

Resetar, Noell, and Pellegrin (2006) as cited by McMahon (2012) observed that children whose parents contributed less time devoted to reading were more likely to have reading problems at school. If they are poor then their parents must work all the day for them, which will be no time to help their children on their homework.

Another thing is the stress they have and their family at home. This may affect their grades because no one helps them or even, sometimes, care about their success in schools (Jensen, 2013). In addition, Abraham, Crais and Vernon-Feagans (2013) concur that mothers with low income are using simple sentences and vocabularies with their children. On the other hand, complex sentences and vocabularies are used from high-income mothers with their children.

Given the big population of families with low income, any strategy that seeks to improve life chances and equalize opportunities for children without turning the tide against the growing levels of low income family is going to face an uphill struggle. This occurrence could place greater burden on social services of the government that seek to alleviate various negative effects of inadequate family resources, especially on the education of their children.

Table 5. *Distribution of Respondents' Attitudes Toward Reading*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I think reading is very important.	3.42	0.91	Always
I learn about new things when I read.	3.14	0.86	Often Times
I like to read alone.	2.35	0.96	Sometimes
I read books and magazines every night than watching TV.	2.35	1.03	Sometimes
The pictures are more interesting than the printed words.	2.30	0.82	Sometimes
I only read when I have to.	2.23	0.99	Sometimes
Each week I borrow books from our classroom library.	1.86	1.08	Sometimes
During night time I enjoy TV series than opening my books.	1.86	0.86	Sometimes
My parents read with me each day.	1.76	0.88	Sometimes
I am comfortable reading aloud every time I read.	1.74	0.93	Never
Overall Mean	2.30	0.93	Sometimes

Table 5 exhibits the attitudes of the respondents toward reading. Many respondents have a very positive attitude toward reading with the indicator "I think reading is very important" with a highest mean of 3.42 (SD = 0.91). This implies that the basic goal of reading, which is important, is acquiring new knowledge.

Reading is the foundation of success in school learning. The importance of reading is the idea that the student who leaves school with the ability and willingness to read is the key to lifelong learning. Reading is the process of constructing meaning from a written text. Although readers can identify the words but do not understand what they are reading, they have not achieved the goal of reading. To gain better understanding of the text, readers must possess the foundational knowledge and skills of oral language, where the emphasis shifts to develop fluency. Pupils will become fluent readers when they comprehend what they are reading, can apply and communicate their knowledge and skills in new contexts, and have a strong motivation to read.

Respondents could have experienced anxiety during their turn to read and were ridiculed by their classmates or the teacher over their performance. The main concern of the respondents when reading aloud was to struggle with the script to decode it. Thus, there was considerable attention to both fluency (ability to recognize words automatically) and pronunciation. This situation made the respondents doubtful whether what they are reading "sounds right". As a result, the indicator "I am comfortable reading aloud every time I read" obtained the lowest mean of 1.74 (SD = 0.93) and described as never. Perhaps, some respondents do not understand purpose of the reading aloud activity. They just read because they were told. As Jacobs (2018) states "it is possible to pronounce words without understanding their meaning (known as "barking the print"). Likewise, other students are not listening, but are reading ahead to practice

in case they are called on to read”. Boredom existed when other learners are reading.

Silently reading in parallel with somebody else who is reading aloud is inherently boring when the read aloud reader level of English was insufficient to achieve proper diction and made low sounding out of words that attracted the attention of their classmates. While it is true that classmates are expected to read the same words silently at the same time, silent reading is not the same as reading aloud, which requires different skills.

Attitude, as it relates to reading, is a state of mind accompanied by feelings and emotions which makes reading more or less probable (Schmitt, 2010). Children's personal experiences in reading are directly related to children's attitudes toward reading. If children cannot get access to interesting books with vivid pictures that are related to their lives, cannot read alone and enjoy viewing TV series, they cannot get anything from reading. Gradually, they may form a negative attitude toward reading. Those who perform poorly in reading usually develop negative attitude towards reading, and invariably the development of undesirable reading habits.

Majority of them think reading is carried out mainly for examination purpose. Hence, the generality of learners read only for the achievement of a desired objective—success in examinations. As Owusu-Acheaw and Larson (2014) put it “they only read to pass examination and when quizzed on why they engaged in reading”. Additionally, the result is in line with the study of Petscher (2010) who posits that students need to be equipped with good attitudes in reading which engender good performance in reading comprehension task. Learners who are slow at comprehension will almost possibly develop a feeling of dislike for books and this will most likely prevent them from having adequate practice in reading. This will invariably result in poor standards of reading. It naturally follows then with negative attitude. By implication, the learners are not likely to perform well in reading comprehension task.

McKenna (2011) suggests that ‘if teachers are to be successful in changing children’s attitudes toward reading, they must target the factors that affect those attitudes’; such as feeling self-confident and stimulated to continue reading. They should be self-driven to engage in more reading”.

Table 6. *Distribution of Respondents’ Study Habits*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
The most difficult subject is my focus.	3.00	0.94	Always
In learning new ideas, I look for examples about it.	2.97	1.08	Oftentimes
I study in a quiet place, I don’t like crowded and noisy place.	2.92	0.96	Oftentimes
I take down notes every time my teachers discuss lessons.	2.74	0.98	Oftentimes
I review lessons that I’m going to study, I prepared ahead of time for my daily quiz.	2.68	0.84	Oftentimes
At the start of the week, I carefully think of my subjects to study.	2.67	0.88	Oftentimes
At the place where I study, I only study (I don’t do other things like playing online games or facebook, etc.).	2.61	0.94	Oftentimes
I spent my vacant time in school memorizing than playing outside the classroom.	2.53	0.89	Oftentimes
When things are not understood I refer to the dictionary.	2.48	0.98	Sometimes
After a few errands at home, I directly go open my notebooks.	2.47	0.90	Sometimes
Overall Mean	2.71	0.94	Oftentimes

Legend: Always = 4.00; Oftentimes = 3.00; Sometimes = 3.00; Never = 1.00

As shown in Table 6, most of the respondents have positive study habits as shown on the indicator “The most difficult subject is my focus” with a highest mean of 3.00(SD = 0.94) described as always. Based from their responses, it was revealed that the respondents struggled with new concepts as a natural and necessary part of the learning process. There is no single way to study effectively. But the most important thing to develop in studying is to learn how to focus attention to the most difficult subjects. This suggests structuring the study sessions by prioritizing to study first the subjects that are difficult down to the easiest ones.

Few respondents admitted “sometimes” as responses to the indicator “After a few errands at home, I directly go open my notebooks” with a lowest mean of 2.47(SD = 0.90) described as sometimes. Although few respondents selected the indicator, it was a good indication of developing a consistent good study habit and it would soon become part of the respondent’s routine. These respondents were more motivated to take extra step academically when they perceived that schooling, through hard work can make difference to their life. Once they get used to the cycle, skipping to study in a day would make them feel their day is incomplete.

Table 7 presents the respondents’ parent’s follow-up. Most of the respondents answered “yes” with description of “always” on the indicator “Did they explain to you the importance of coming to school?” with a highest percentage score of 91.00. This result illustrated how parents emphasized the value of going to school as reflected by the responses of their children. Parents always explain to their children that the importance of attending school is to receive an education that helps them throughout every phase of their life. The school is the place where the formal basic foundation of knowledge is imparted. Education is gaining information of looking at life in this world. But, information cannot be converted into knowledge without education. Education makes people capable of interpreting the perspectives of looking at life. Learning also focused on the values, attitudes and behaviors which enable people to learn to live together. By obtaining knowledge, a person is in a better position to attain good overall development (Hanushek, Schwerdt, Woessmann & Zhang, 2016).

Table 7. *Distribution of Respondents' Parent's Follow-up*

Indicators	Yes (%)	Description	No (%)	Description
Did they explain to you the importance of coming to school?	91.00	Always	9.00	Never
Do your parents monitor your homework?	87.88	Always	12.12	Never
Were you given nutritious meals and require you adequate time to sleep?	83.33	Always	16.67	Never
Are they checking to ensure your excellent attendance in school?	80.30	Always	19.70	Never
Did they attend your scheduled HRPTA Meeting?	74.24	Frequently	25.76	Never
Do your parents read with you, encourage you to pay attention on what you read?	72.72	Frequently	27.28	Seldom
Are they familiar with the grading system used on your quarterly report card?	69.69	Frequently	30.31	Seldom
Do your parents participate on the Parents'-School activities such as local Barangay Fiesta and Family Day?	66.67	Frequently	33.33	Seldom
Are they aware of your academic strengths and weaknesses?	65.15	Frequently	34.85	Seldom
Are they aware of the school policies?	63.63	Frequently	36.37	Seldom
Overall	75.46	Frequently	21.84	Never

Good education is the key to a better job and a higher standard of living for many people. A school environment offers students the opportunity to learn to work with others, which is a very important “real world” skill. School is not only important to specific individual but also it helps society progress by educating its members who bring their newly acquired knowledge and skills to the workforce (Carlson, Dahl & Rooth, 2012). Today’s increasingly technical and specified society, the job market no longer allows for unskilled, uneducated laborers to do well.

Few respondents answered the indicator “Are they aware of your school policies?” which obtained a lowest percentage score of 63.63 with the description of “frequently”. This implies that respondent’s parents do not know the school policies that affect their children’s performance in school. One explanation could be the unavailable time due to the demanding work schedule of their parents to know the school policies or it could be that the school does not give much information to parents.

The common school policies familiar to both students and faculty are attendance, discipline, and grading. The decisions that the school makes regarding established policies affect students enormously. Teachers' instructional decisions influenced students' feelings about the curriculum, but the policies in both classrooms and in the entire school provided the context for teacher-student interactions around instruction. Also, policies structure the parent’s relationship with the school. The overall percentage score of the “yes” option is 75.46 with a scale description as “frequently”. This implies that the indicators are not commonly performed by parents to their children.

This results of the study provided information of the need to inform parents about reading development and instruction. This will help them to have a better understanding of their children’s progress and to actively participate in the school system. Sullivan (2012) articulates that parents have shared responsibility in educating their children rather than delegating this authority solely to the school. Parental knowledge about reading is crucial because, between grades three and six, students’ confidence in their reading ability decreased. This may be due to the fact that younger students have unrealistic beliefs about their reading skills, but become more objective with age. Likewise, Henderson and Map (2010) suggest parents to talk to their children about school, expect them to do well and make sure that out-of-school activities are constructive. When schools engage families in ways that are linked to improving learning, students make greater gains. When schools build partnerships with families that respond to their concerns and honor their contributions, they are successful in sustaining connections that are aimed at improving student achievement.

Table 8. *Distribution of Respondents' Availability of Reading Materials*

Indicators	Yes (%)	Description	No (%)	Description
Does your home have crayons and pencils readily available for writing and drawing?	86.36	Always	13.64	Never
Do you have at least one alphabet book (e.g. Dr. Seuss’s ABC book)?	71.21	Frequently	28.79	Seldom
Do have books of your own like dictionary, encyclopedias, magazines, newspapers and novels?	59.09	Frequently	40.91	Seldom
Do you keep newsletter in your school?	42.43	Seldom	57.57	Frequently
Do you have collections of coloring and rhyme books?	30.31	Seldom	69.69	Frequently
Do you have at least 20 picture books?	27.28	Seldom	72.72	Frequently
Do your parents post concept charts on your wall for shapes, colors and body charts?	27.73	Seldom	72.27	Frequently
Do you have flipcharts to read at home?	18.19	Never	81.81	Always
Can we find a little library in your house?	15.16	Never	84.84	Always
Do you collect recipe cards, coupon or cook book to read?	12.12	Never	87.88	Always
Overall	38.98	Never	53.78	Frequently

Table 8 reveals the respondents’ availability of reading materials. The indicator “Does your home have crayons and pencils readily available for writing and drawing?” obtained the highest percentage score of 86.36 which is described as “always”.

Typically every home where there are children who go to school has crayons and pencils available for writing and drawing. Although crayons and pencils are identified as ordinary materials of young learners, they are considered very useful in terms of educational applications. The OT Toolbox (2015) enumerated the many developmental benefits of coloring for children as: (1) Bilateral coordination is skill in using both hands together in a coordinated manner needed for handwriting, scissor use, and many functional tasks. A child needs to hold the paper with one hand as he colors. Using the non-dominant hand as a stabilizer allows a child to build strength and dexterity in their dominant hand. This skill will carry over to writing tasks, and makes coloring a great activity for kids who are switching hands in activities; (2) Tripod pencil grasp is developed when a child holds a crayon. He is working on the strength of the intrinsic muscles of the hand.

The tripod grip is the most common configuration of the fingers on the pencil shaft. The pencil shaft is supported between the thumb and the middle finger and the forefinger rests on the top of the pencil shaft. The fingers are able to move freely, while the ring and little fingers curl gently into the palm, giving the hand stability; (3) spatial awareness is a visual perception through the hand-eye coordination. When writing or coloring, children must coordinate their physical movements with information received from their visual system. Controlled movements are essential for handwriting, letter formation, and neatness in handwriting. Coloring helps with practicing coordination of the visual input with physical movements of the hands in very small spaces or large areas; and (4) Creativity and Self-Confidence are developed during coloring. A blank piece of paper and a box of crayons can inspire stories and pictures. Being creative allows a child to build their self-confidence in other areas, especially handwriting and pencil tasks.

Few respondents indicate a “yes” reply with the description of “always” to the indicator “Do you collect recipe cards, coupon or cookbook to read?” This indicator gathered the lowest percentage score of 12.12. The collection of recipe cards, coupon or cookbook suggest that respondents willing to cook the recipe. This implies that the respondents belonged to well-income family, considering the usual expensive ingredients to be used. The overall percentage is 38.98 and 53.78 of the “yes” option and “no” option, respectively. The description of both options, which is never and frequently, indicates that many of the reading materials were not available or obtainable to the respondents.

The learning materials are critical ingredients in education and the intended objectives cannot be easily implemented without them. No meaningful learning takes place without adequate resource materials. Adequate learning resources have an impact on academic performance

McMullan (2010) made a conclusion regarding the consequence of inaccessibility of reading materials to reading achievement. "There is now considerable evidence that the amount and quality of students' access to reading materials is substantively related to the amount of reading they engage in, which in turn is the most important determinant of reading achievement". It was also found from the study of Teaneck (2010) that there is a direct link between the number of books at home and the reading development of that child. The availability and accessibility of the reading materials at home is the cornerstone of a successful family reading culture. With regard to this, parents are advised to create a healthy reading environment at home by starting with a good supply of reading materials like newspapers, magazines and books regardless whether they are owned or borrowed, new or used. The important thing is that reading materials are a natural part of their home and daily lives.

Table 9. *Distribution of Respondents' Availability of Gadgets*

Indicators	Yes (%)	Description	No (%)	Description
Do you have TV, Radio and ordinary cell phone?	81.81	Always	18.19	Never
Do you have headphone for listening sounds?	80.30	Always	19.70	Never
Do you have smart phones and smart TV at home?	40.91	Seldom	59.09	Frequently
Do you have DigiCam or Android phone?	30.31	Seldom	69.69	Frequently
Do you have MP3 or MP4 for music playing?	27.28	Seldom	72.72	Frequently
Are you using Bluetooth speaker with microphone in singing at home?	21.22	Never	78.78	Always
Are you using laptop or I pad or tablet connected to Internet in research at home?	18.19	Never	81.81	Always
Do your appliances have visual timers already?	13.64	Never	86.36	Always
Are you using personal printers for printing documents?	12.12	Never	87.88	Always
Do you have Interactive Book System (Talking Book)?	10.61	Never	89.39	Always
Overall	33.64	Seldom	66.36	Frequently

As displayed in Table 9, majority of the respondents replied “yes” with description of “always” on the indicator; “Do you have TV, Radio and ordinary cell phone? with a highest percentage score of 81.81. Owning a radio, TV and cell phone became basic gadgets to the middle-income family due to their numerous day-to-day applications to household activities. However, thinking about the high cost of acquiring electronic gadgets is a nightmare to the low income of many respondents’ family.

Few respondents gave a “never” response to the indicator “Do you have Interactive Book System (Talking Book)?” with a lowest percentage score of 10.61. Talking books guide children how to entertain themselves without the presence of another person while to learn. They learn independently and can also be checked. Talking books contain large amount of information that is not in written form, but only recorded (Solcova & Magdin, 2016). However, acquiring the expensive electronic gadget was beyond the limits of the monthly

family income of the respondents. Generally, the respondents disclosed “seldom” response in the “yes” option which is interpreted as hardly ever existing. Similarly the “frequently” response in the “no” option is construed as not normally applied and available.

Technology inspired gadgets have been proven to be very helpful in educating student. They can access the educational websites and can get detailed information about required topic. Technology makes things better as have access to pile of material and can be very useful in understanding things better (Chen, 2012). Visual presentations, educational videos, interactive programs, learning tutorial and variety of books available all the time on internet has revolutionized education in a better way. Educational games help students to perform well in their studies. As they can have many online quizzes available, online tutorials and brainstorming riddle.

The improper use of these gadgets may cause negative effects on health and learning outcomes. Students use gadgets for various purposes like playing games, watching videos, listening songs, chatting with their friends, browsing different websites. They spend most of their time in these activities and don't pay attention to their posture, screen brightness, and screen distance from their eyes which ultimately affect their vision and health. Staring at electronic screen continuously for long time causes eye irritation and chance of myopia also increases in children when they spend about 8 hours daily on gadgets. When people use electronic screens, they blink less. On an average, a person blinks about 15 times in a minute. Due to the high attention required while using an electronic screen, this rate can drop to less than 5 times in a minute (Jonathan & Andrew, 2016). Possible negative effects of excessive use of electronic gadgets to learning are Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). This refers to a mental disorder that creates problems like inattentive, excess activity or has difficulty controlling behavior which is not appropriate. Students show aggression or appear tense when they cannot get online and this feeling goes off when their devices are connected (Sundus, 2018).

The findings of the study disclosed that the many respondents do not have the mentioned gadgets used to promote reading skills. Since majority of the respondent's families belonged to the monthly income bracket from Php 5,001 to Php 10,000.00, there was difficulty to acquire the gadgets. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2015), the national poverty threshold in 2015 stood at P10, 969 per month, meaning a family of five needed to earn that much to be able to eat, have shelter, travel, buy medicine, or go to school, among other life necessities. This is the most popular problem for students. Not all of them can have electronic gadgets (laptop computers, Ipad) or other technology in their homes (Demski, 2011). While education these days depends on technology especially when they have homework or research paper should be done at home. However, not all the families can provide this technology for their children. So, student's success depends on what their family can give them. Thus, the family income can play an important role in student's achievement.

Problem 2. What is the performance of the Grade IV pupils in the pretest and posttest conducted to the following groups: control, and experimental?

Table 10. *Distribution of Respondents' Performance in the Pretest conducted to the Control and Experimental Groups*

Pre test Scores	Performance Level	Control Group		Experimental Group		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
0 - 19	Poor	14	42.42	19	57.58	33	50.00
20 - 24	Fair	18	54.55	12	36.36	30	45.45
25 - 29	Good	1	3.03	2	6.06	3	4.55
30 - 34	Very Good	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
35 - 40	Excellent	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Looking at the Table 10, the group distribution of respondents in terms of their pretest scores in the control group and the experimental group. The control group achieved adequate pretest scores than the experimental group. Result disclosed that 14(42.42%) of the respondents have poor pretest performance in the control group and 19(57.58%) of the respondents in the experimental group. For the combined group, 33(50.00%) of the respondents have poor performance (0-19), 30 (45.45%) of them have fair performance (20-24) and only 3(4.55%) of them have good performance (25-29). No respondents attained the very good and excellent performance level. As to their mean pretest scores the control group attained 19.39 which was slightly higher compared to the experimental group which has only a pretest mean of 18.58.

Problem 3. What is the performance of the Grade IV pupils in the posttest conducted to the following groups: intensive reading approach, and traditional approach?

At a close scrutiny of Table 11, the group distribution of respondents in terms of their posttest scores in the control group and the experimental group, both the control group and the experimental group achieved substantial difference. There were 32(96.97%) respondents in the experimental group who attained excellent performance level, while only 17(51.52%) respondents in the control group were listed. These findings indicated that the experimental group considerably outperformed the control group.

The results of this study indicate that intensive reading approach has positive effect on the Grade IV pupils' reading comprehension development. In other words, the results indicated that intensive approach made contribution in increasing the reading comprehension. The respondents in the intensive reading approach group improved their performance in the posttest significantly after the intensive reading approach was implemented, whereas the respondents in the traditional control group improved minimally their reading

performance. Thus, the findings portray the intensive reading approach as a viable method for enhancing the reading comprehension of the Grade IV pupils. These results are congruent with previous research confirming the positive effect of intensive reading on reading comprehension achievement of Li (2010) which indicates that the learners' ability to use intensive reading strategy is critical factor determining their reading comprehension. Thus, the close relationship between intensive reading and reading comprehension provided support for the possibility that educators should enhance learners' reading comprehension.

Table 11. *Distribution of Respondents' Performance in the Posttest Conducted to the Control and Experimental Groups*

Posttest Scores	Performance Level	Control Group		Experimental Group		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
0 - 19	Poor	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20 - 24	Fair	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
25 - 29	Good	2	6.06	0.00	0.00	2	3.03
30 - 34	Very Good	14	42.42	1	3.03	15	22.73
35 - 40	Excellent	17	51.52	32	96.97	49	74.24

Problem 4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the Grade IV pupils to intensive reading approach and to those who are in the traditional group in the pre test and posttest conducted?

Since the researcher needs to know what the respondents know and can do before beginning the study, pretesting was administered. Pretesting the respondents is a method of discovering and assessing their prior knowledge or level of understanding about the subject to be studied. Pretests helped measure the respondent's learning over a period of time. Similarly, pretest gave the respondents a preview of what will be expected during conduct of the study. The pretest was the respondent's first exposure to key terms and concepts, and the more frequent the exposure, the more likely they will retain the information. To find out if the control group and the experimental group are homogeneous to start with, a paired t-test analysis was performed as shown in Table 11.

Table 12. *Comparison of the Respondents' Performance in the Pretest Conducted to the Control and Experimental Groups*

Group	PreTest Scores		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Remark
	Mean	SD				
Control	19.39	3.66	0.81	1.30	0.20	Not Significant
Experimental	18.58	3.78				

The comparison of the respondents' performance in the pretest is shown in Table 12. The difference in the pretest means between the control group and the experimental group was not statistically significant because the P value of 0.20 was higher than 0.05. Therefore, it is confirmed that the two groups are homogeneous. Simply taken, before the beginning of the treatment (intensive reading), both the control group and the experimental groups were of the same level at their reading ability. Hence, any subsequent differences between the control group and the experimental group can be attributed to the treatment (intensive reading) that they would receive.

Homogeneous grouping is implemented to help educators teach a group of students at a comparable instructional level. Hornby, Witte, and Mitchell (2011) opined that some of the reasons that homogeneous grouping has been utilized in the educational setting were to meet the specific academic needs of students, and reduce the boredom of advanced students. While the above reasons are targeting the academic needs of students, research has indicated that, more often than not, grouping students into classrooms based on ability has not shown a significant difference.

Table 13. *Comparison of the Respondents' Performance in the Posttest Conducted to the Control and Experimental Groups*

Group	Post Test Scores		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Remark
	Mean	SD				
Control	35.03	2.47	-2.36	5.57	0.00	Significant
Experimental	37.39	1.50				

Table 13 shows the comparison of the respondents' performance in the posttest. It is evident from the table that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean of the control group and the experimental group in their posttest performance at $p < 0.05$ level. The respondents in the experimental group achieved statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) higher mean scores. Statistical significant result (the difference) is the outcome when the computed p-value is equal or less than the established significance level of 0.05. Accordingly, if the null hypothesis is true, there really is no difference. In this study the computed p-value was 0.00, which is lower than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis that states no significant difference between the performances of the Grade IV pupils exposed to intensive reading approach and to those who are in the control group was rejected. This implies that intensive reading had a positive influence on the learners reading comprehension because they have actually improved significantly. This also confirms that the changes in the mean have shown that experimental group had a positive effect and can promote students' reading comprehension.

This study has revealed that intensive reading instruction can improve learners' reading comprehension. Similarly the literature has

disclosed that the situation at primary level demands knowledge of reading strategies in order to be successful as learners are exposed to huge volumes of reading material. The results of this study suggest that intensive reading can improve the learners' reading comprehension. This suggests that teachers need to design reading instruction that focuses on intensive reading. The results of the study have shown that those learners who used the intensive reading approach comprehend the texts they read better than those who use traditional approach. This requires that teachers should help learners identify their reading approaches. Having that information will assist the teachers in designing reading instruction that focuses on reading comprehension to new learners.

The result of the present study is in line with the study conducted by Consoli and Dioni (2010). They found that intensive reading is useful to improve students reading comprehension especially in teaching reading to beginners. It is also noted that through intensive reading, it can provide a base for students to improve a better control of language and finally, for checking the degree of comprehension individually (Vaughn, 2012).

Problem 5. To what extent does intensive reading approach contribute to Grade IV pupils reading comprehension?

Intensive reading is to make the pupils more understand the content of the text effectively, to get the successfulness in reading comprehension by the accurate argumentation. In this study, the students read the text intensively by themselves and answer the questions based on the text to know the students' comprehension in reading activity. Intensive reading approach helped the pupils to improve their reading comprehension in comprehending English text. As revealed by comparing the respondents' performance in the posttest, the performances of the Grade IV pupils exposed to intensive reading approach achieved statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) higher mean scores. This implies that intensive reading had a positive influence on the pupils reading comprehension because they have actually improved significantly. Simply taken, those pupils who participated in the intensive reading approach have better comprehension to the texts they read than those pupils who participated in the traditional approach. It can be deduced that intensive reading improved the reading ability of the pupils because they can find the meaning in every word of the text and it is challenging and interesting especially in descriptive text. Furthermore, the pupils can work with their friends to improve their communication and motivation in reading.

Practically, the outcome of this study is expected to give a good feedback and widely knowledge and strategy to English language teachers, especially those who teach at elementary grade levels. Indeed, reading comprehension is very vital for the learning process as it provides pupils with the ability to understand, criticize and interact with the text; it expands pupils' trends and experience; it enhances their commonsense level; it deepens their thinking and assists them to orientate and monitor themselves while reading; it helps pupils comprehend a text self dependently and the teachers develop clear and successive instructional procedures and it breaks the pupils' inaction by encouraging them to get involved in the educational process more actively and effectively. Hence, utilizing intensive reading approach that improves reading comprehension level within the pupils is very necessary. Moreover, intensive reading can help pupils write better, as well as improve their listening and speaking ability. They may develop positive attitudes toward reading in English and increased motivation to study.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions are given below:

The pretest scores of the respondents were considered as poor and fair performance but later became very good to excellent as shown by the posttest scores results. The study revealed that there is a significant effect on the performance of the respondents when intensive reading approach was applied considering the difference of the pre-test and post-test results. This indicates that the application of intensive reading has a positive influence on the learners reading comprehension because they have actually improved significantly. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the performance of the Grade IV pupils exposed to intensive reading approach and to those who are in the traditional group was rejected.

Based on the findings and conclusion obtained in the study, the following recommendations are given below:

1. School administrators should design a comprehensive reading comprehension program with strong emphasis on the application of intensive reading. They should conduct teacher training seminars about the implementation of intensive reading as intervention program for pupils with poor reading ability.
2. Supervisors and principals should encourage elementary teachers in the lower grade level to employ the intensive reading approach to increase reading comprehension skills.
3. English teachers should convince pupils to participate on intensive reading activities to enhance their reading comprehension ability.
4. Future researchers should conduct further studies on the intensive reading by expanding the schematic diagram to include the impact on socio-economic status of the respondent's family and the availability of instructional resources in school.

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